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Comprehensive analysis of Land Surface Temperature with different indices using Landsat – 8 (OLI / TIRS) data in Kanpur Metropolis, India

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ABSTRACT

Urbanization has a significant impact on land use by interchanging areas of vegetation with residential and commercial landscape which reflects a heterogeneous urban infrastructure; this escalates the land Surface Temperature (LST), which has become major Eco-environmental anxiety. Hence, the study of Land Surface Temperature (LST) and its correlation with other indices in urban areas using satellite data is more important. The present study focuses on the relation of LST with the selected indices based on Landsat 8 OLI (Operational Land Imager) and TIRS (Thermal Infrared Sensor) data in Kanpur Metropolis, India. These satellites data of October 20 were computed and analyzed through regression analysis between LST and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI), Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), and Normalized Difference Soil Index (NDSI). LST retrieved by thermal data examination which represents the spatiotemporal distribution of surface temperature. Mean LST varied from 33.94 °C to 24.12°C. NDBI is reciting the built-up index and NDVI the proportion of vegetation in the Metropolis area. Correlation results of LST with NDBI, NDSI, and NDBI with NDSI, NDWI have shown a strong positive relationship i.e. 0.74, 0.72, 0.89 and 0.64 respectively along with the $R^2 = 0.545, 0.525, 0.787, \text{ and } 0.407$ respectively, whereas the correlation of, NDVI with NDBI and NDWI has a strong negative relationship i.e. -0.76 and -0.98 respectively along with the. $R^2 = 0.575$ and 0.9615 . A Global Moran's I and LISA Index analysis was done for all of the indicators.

Keywords: Land surface Temperature (LST); Vegetation Index (NDVI), Built up Index (NDBI), Water Index (NDWI), Soil Index (NDSI), Moran's I Index, LISA

1. Introduction

Urban Heat Island (UHI) refers to the urban areas which have higher temperatures at the interface between the Earth's surface and its atmosphere than the surrounding suburban or rural areas due to increase in urbanization and industrialization. Urbanization has led to the replacement of land covers with artificial built-up surfaces made up of impervious materials and a decrease of vegetation which helps in reducing temperatures due to evapotranspiration (Voogt and Oke, 2003). Nowadays urbanization has become a common phenomenon, since the 20th century, about 50% of the population living in urban areas in the present decade. Rapid urbanization leads to an increase in Land Surface Temperature (LST), which is governed by surface latent and sensible heat fluxes. LST is a significant parameter in all physical processes of surface energy and water balance at local and global scales (Brunsell, et al. 2003; Karnieli et al., 2010). It has wide application in several fields viz; evapotranspiration, climate change, hydrological cycle, vegetation monitoring, urban climate, and environmental studies (Bastiaanssen, et al., 1998; Weng, et al., 2009). Satellite based TIR data is directly related to the LST through the radiative transfer equation.

Previous studies suggest that there exists a strong negative correlation between NDVI and LST, while NDVI changes greatly with the season. Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) and Enhanced vegetation index (EVI) have been used as an indicator for vegetation cover and Normalized difference built-up index (NDBI) for the level of urbanization accompanied correlation analyses among four land cover indices i.e. normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), normalized difference water index (NDWI), normalized difference built index (NDBI), and LST.

A number of techniques have been developed to assess the spatial variations in remotely sensed imagery. Because a landscape is regularized into a grid of similarly sized and frequently spaced pixels, there must be a certain degree of dependency between pixels (Wulder and Boots, 1998) LISA measures the local spatial auto-correlation and indicates the discrete spatial regimes.

Consequently, this present study analyzes the potential of LANDSAT-8 TIRS in the mapping of LST and interprets their relationship with selected indices that is NDVI, NDBI, NDWI, and NDSI using ArcGIS 10.8 software.

2. Study area:

The Kanpur Metropolis of the industrial capital of Uttar Pradesh, interpenetrate a very significant position in Northern India. This Metropolis is situated on the right bank of eternal Ganga River, as well as the Metropolis lies between the doab of River Ganga and River Pandu, stands as one of the North-India's major industrial (mainly lather industry)center with its own historical, religious and commercial importance. The geographical location of the study area situated between latitudes of 26° 10' and 26° 36'N and longitudes of 79° 30' and 80° 35'E covers an area of over 650 sq.the elevation varied from elevation is 95 to 154 m (Fig. 1.0). This fifth most highly-populated Metropolis's administratively divided into 6 zones and 110 wards (the inner core area of Kanpur constitutes 67 wards) with an average ward population range of 20000 to 26000. However, the Kanpur urban agglomeration, as defined by the Census of 2011, has a population of 29,20,067 persons and area is comprised of Kanpur municipal corporation (KMC), Kanpur municipal corporation outgrowth (KMCO), Kanpur cantonment board (KCB), Armapur estate, northern railway colony, and Chakeri.

The mean daily maximum and minimum temperature in May is 41.7 °C and 27.20C respectively, and the maximum temperature rises up to 45 °C or over. The average annual temperature of the study region is 25 °C with January (7.75 °C) being the coldest month and May and June being the hottest (38.85 °C) months. The average annual rainfall in the district is 872.10 mm rainfall occurs mainly in monsoon months. The climate is sub-humid and it is characterized by hot summer and general dryness except in the southwest monsoon. About 90% of rainfall takes place from the third week of June to September.

Fig. 1 The location map of Kanpur Metropolis

3. Methodology:

3.1 Data resources and pre-processing:

This study uses images from Landsat 8 OLI / TIRS on 2020-10-25 from United States Geological Survey (USGS, <http://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>). The path/row was 144/42. The authors used ArcGIS 10.8, ERDAS imagine 14, Microsoft Office 2010, IBM SPSS statistics 26, GeoDa and Origin2021 software to complete radiometric correction of the remote sensing images, to carry out this study. During the pre-processing of datasets, the gray value or digit number (DN) of the multispectral bands, converted into the reflectivity values of the sensor are used (Fast Line-of-sight Atmospheric).

3.2 Determination of NDVI, NDBI, NDWI, and NDSI:

NDVI become very popular to monitor vegetation statuses, it is less sensitive to the changes in atmospheric conditions than other indices. Furthermost researchers recommend that the NDVI is sensitive to low density vegetation, and it is particularly suitable for urban areas with high densities of built-up land (Wang et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2017). NDBI is very useful for mapping the urban built-up areas (Zha et al., 2003; Zha, Gao, and Ni et al. 2003; Himanshu et. al., 2019). NDWI is generally used for water body extraction (Gao, 1996; McFeeters1996). NDSI has been used to detect signature changes in un-mixing urban marsh from satellite images (Ruchi et al., 2018). The values of NDBI,

NDWI, and NDSI can vary from - 1 to + 1. The equation of these these four indices was presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Equations for estimating different Indices

Acronym	Description	Equations	Reference
NDVI	Normalized difference vegetation index	$(\rho_{NIR} - \rho_{Red}) / (\rho_{NIR} + \rho_{Red})$	Giannini et al., 2015; Hanqiu et al., 2019
NDBI	Normalized difference built-up index	$(\rho_{SWIR_1} - \rho_{NIR}) / (\rho_{SWIR_1} + \rho_{NIR})$	Zha, Gao, and Ni et al. 2003; Himanshu et. al., 2019
NDWI	Normalized difference water index	$(\rho_{Green} - \rho_{NIR}) / (\rho_{Green} + \rho_{NIR})$	Gao, 1996; McFeeters 1996
NDSI	Normalized difference soil index	$(\rho_{SWIR_2} - \rho_{Green}) / (\rho_{SWIR_2} + \rho_{Green})$	Ruchi et al., 2018

3.3 Land surface temperature (LST):

The standard method for recovering LST from raw Landsat datasets requires the conversion of the DN values of the TIRS bands (Bands 10 and 11 in Landsat 8 data) into at-satellite spectral radiance values (L_λ) (Chander et al., 2009; Xu et al., 2009; USGS, 2016b; Mohammad Zare, et al., 2019) and then into the at-satellite brightness temperature (BT), which is calculated beneath an assumption of unity emissivity (ϵ) and using pre-launch calibration constants (Chander et al., 2009; Xu et al., 2009; USGS, 2016b). For conversion from a satellite temperature to land surface temperature as well as DNs to radiance the following equation was used (USGS. Landsat 8 Data users Handbook, 2016):

$$L_\lambda = M_L * Q_{cat} + A_L \quad (5)$$

Where, L_λ is spectral radiation (Watts/ (m²*sr* μ m)), M_L is Band specific multiplicative rescaling factor from the metadata, Where 'n' is the band number. (10 or 11 for Landsat 8), Q_{cat} = Level 1 value in DN or Corresponds to band 10 & 11, and A_L is Band specific additive rescaling factor from the metadata.

TIRS data were converted from spectral radiance to brightness temperature (BT_i):

$$BT_i = \{K_2 / \ln [(K_1/L_\lambda) + 1]\} - 273.15 \text{ (in } ^\circ\text{C)} \quad (6)$$

Where, BT_i is top of atmosphere (TOA) brightness temperature for TIRS band i (is 10 & 11 for TIRS) in Kelvin or Degree Celsius, K_1 = Band specific coefficients are thermal conversion constant from the metadata. Where 'n' is the band Number 10 or 11 for Landsat - 8 (Table 2), K_2 = Band specific thermal conversion constant from the metadata.

Table 2: The values of λ , Quantized calibration pixel and Spectral radiance for Landsat bands

Satellite	Band	λ (μ m)	Thermal conversion constants (Parameter i)	
			K1	K2
Landsat - 8 (OLI/TIRS)	10	10.895	774.8853	1321.0789
	11	12.005	480.8883	1201.1442

Source: NASA (2013), USGA (2015)

Calculated to P_v from NDVI values obtained in formula 1. Proportion of vegetation in mixed pixels to be estimated using the equation (Zahir, 2020):

$$P_v = \left(\frac{(NDVI - NDVI \text{ minimum})}{(NDVI \text{ maximum} - NDVI \text{ minimum})} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Where, P_v are the Proportion of Vegetation, NDVI is the DN values from NDVI Image, NDVI minimum and maximum value is minimum and maximum DN values from NDVI Image, respectively.

LST is the average emissivity (ϵ) of an element of the earth surface calculated from NDVI values. NDVI is expressed as the equation:

$$\mathcal{E} = 0.004 * P_v + 0.986 \quad (8)$$

The LST is the radiative temperature which calculated using TOA brightness temperature (BT), wavelength of emitted radiance, LST is calculated using equation (Orhan and Yakar, 2016):

$$LST = BT_i / [1 + (\lambda * BT / C_2) * \ln(\mathcal{E})] \quad (9)$$

Where, BT is TOA brightness temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), λ = Wavelength of emitted radiance (Table -2), $C_2 = h * c / s = 14387.685 \mu\text{m K}$; h = Planck's constant = $6.626 * 10^{-34} \text{Js}$; s = Boltzmann constant = $1.38 * 10^{-23} \text{J/k}$; c = Velocity of light = $2.998 * 10^8 \text{m/s}$.

3.4 Global spatial auto-correlation (Moran's I index):

The coefficient of Global Moran's I simultaneously expressed the correlation of attributes values for the spatial neighboring unit, which can be calculated by the above equations (Gong et al., 2014; Jonathan et al., 2020; Yunqing et al., 2020):

$$\text{Global Moran's } I_i = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m W_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})}{S^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m W_{ij}} \quad (10)$$

$$S^2 = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \quad (11)$$

Where, x_i is the attribute value of the neighboring space of i ; n is the total number of the grids in the study area; \bar{x} is the average of the x_i over the n space; W_{ij} is the weight of the matrix, which can represent the relationship of spatial objects; $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$.

3.5 Local Indicators of spatial autocorrelation (LISA index):

It can analyze the value of global Moran's I at the correlation of neighborhood values around a specific spatial location, which can effectively reflect the local spatial association (Gong et al., 2014). The foremost equations are expressed as (Anselin, 1995; Gong et al., 2014):

$$\text{Local Moran's } I_i = \frac{x_i - \bar{x}}{S_i^2} \sum_{j=1, i \neq j}^N W_{ij} (x_j - \bar{x}) \quad (12)$$

$$S_i^2 = \frac{\sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^N W_{ij}}{n-1} - \bar{x}^2 \quad (13)$$

$$W_{ij}(d) = \frac{1}{dm} \quad (14)$$

Where, I_i represents the spatial clustering of similar values (High or Low value) around the spatial unit, negative I_i represents the spatial clustering between dissimilar values, x_i is an attribute for feature i , \bar{x} is the mean of the corresponding attribute, $w_{i,j}$ is the spatial weight between feature i and j , n equating to the total number of features.

4. Results and discussions:

The results obtained from the analysis are discussed below:

4.1 Land surface temperature (LST):

The outcome of the present research of the study Metropolis's has been to produce and computed an absolute LST map is illustrated in Fig. 2 (B). The urban areas of the Metropolis show LST higher than the vegetated areas and water body but lower than the bare land areas. Respectively, in the years Oct. 2020, LST values showed ranges between 24.12°C to 33.94°C , the minimum and SD temperature is 28.66 and 1.223 respectively and Moran's I index is 0.40 , indicating that there was a moderately positive correlation, the spatial distribution is clustered rather than random (Fig. 3.A). In order to study the relation of LST with the respective indices, 3D scatter plots were obtained for LST with NDVI, NDBI, NDWI, and NDSI and are shown in Fig.6 respectively. LISA cluster Map and Significant level map reflects the spatial distribution of the LST values (Fig. 4&5).

4.2 NDVI and LST Relationship:

NDVI is a measure of the quantity and strength of vegetation at the surface. The minimum and maximum range of NDVI varies from -0.114 to 0.412 , and mean and SD is 0.161 and 0.069 respectively. Moran's I is 0.340 , indicating that there was a weak correlation, the spatial distribution is clustered rather than random (Fig. 3.B). NDVI is very sensitive to changes and variations of NDVI might cause changes in land surface temperature. NDVI and LST has strong negative correlation -0.48 and $R^2 = 0.226$. From our observations, high surface temperature was observed in built-up and bare land surfaces whereas green vegetative areas is observed low surface temperature (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Elevation, LST, NDVI, NDBI, NDWI, and NDSI value of the Kanpur Metropolis

4.3 NDVI and NDBI Relationship:

Relationship between NDVI and NDBI has also been developed during the study. The minimum and maximum range of NDBI varies from -0.347 to 0.204, mean and SD is - 0.050 and 0.065 respectively. NDVI have shown strong negative relationship with NDBI- 0.76 and. $R^2 = 0.575$. NDVI can be used to characterize the evolution and expansion of built-up land. Correlation of NDVI Vs NDBI is displaying in the 3D scatter plot (Fig. 6).

4.4 NDBI and LST Relationship:

During the study relationship between NDBI and LST was developed and found a direct relationship between them. The NDBI results have displayed the maximum surface temperature in Built-Up areas. Therefore, it has been predicted that built-up areas or urbanization are inducing much surface temperature variations. In NDBI & LST correlation a strong positive relationship 0.74 (Fig. 3.F) and $R^2 = 0.545$. This relationship of both indices indicates that built-up area is generating much surface temperature variations and is the key contributor in urban heat island. On the other hand, healthy vegetative cover plays a key role in lowering the surface temperature.

Fig. 3. Moran's I scatterplots and Pearson's correlation of different indices in Kanpur Metropolis

4.5 NDWI and LST Relationship:

Positive values of NDWI with lower LST shows in water bodies, whereas other land covers show negative values. This illuminates the non-linear behavior of LST with NDWI. Therefore, NDWI can't be used in the study of LST in urban areas. NDWI can explain LST in those urban areas with no vegetation cover because bare land, urban, and water have a linear relation of LST with NDWI.

4.6 NDSI and LST Relationship:

Water bodies show very low negative values for NDSI whereas bare land shows very high positive NDSI values. Urban areas have NDSI values near to zero with positive as well as negative values of NDSI. Vegetation shows negative values of NDSI near to zero. The minimum and maximum range of NDBI varies from -0.325 to 0.363, mean and SD are 0.008 and 0.060 respectively. Correlation of LST with NDSI has shown a strong positive relationship 0.72 and $R^2 = 0.525$.

4.7 NDBI and NDSI Relationship:

NDBI with NDSI has shown strong positive relationship 0.89 and $R^2 = 0.787$.

4.8 NDBI and NDWI Relationship:

Relationship between NDBI and NDWI has also been developed during the study. The minimum and maximum range of NDWI varies from -0.366 to 0.144, mean and SD is - 0.149 and 0.060 respectively. NDBI with NDWI has shown strong positive relationship 0.64 and $R^2 = 0.407$.

4.9 NDVI and NDWI Relationship:

NDVI with NDWI has a strong negative relationship - 0.98 and $R^2 = 0.9615$.

Fig. 4 Local Spatial Auto-correlation (LISA) Cluster Map in Kanpur Metropolis

The weakly affinity of LST with NDVI and NDWI was observed because the NDVI and NDWI values of higher LST pixels that are urban and bare land lies between two lower LST pixels i.e. vegetation and water bodies. Therefore, NDVI and NDWI are found not suitable for the study of the LST in heterogeneous urban land cover. LST with NDBI and NDSI was a positive correlation, it's observed because the land covers (LC) with positive NDBI and NDSI values show higher LST although those with negative NDBI and NDSI values show lower LST. The correlation was found greater for NDBI than NDSI. In accordance with NDBI, water pixels show higher NDBI than vegetated pixels but LST is lower for water pixels than vegetated pixels which result in poorer R^2 . Among the circumstance of NDSI, water, vegetation, dry land, as well as urban pixels, shows a positive relation with LST making it much appropriate for the study of LST in urban areas. Without water bodies, NDBI can also explain urban LST better in regions.

LISA Cluster Map can subconsciously reflect the spatial distribution of "High-High", "Low - Low", "High-Low", and "Low-High" since the LISA significance map can reflect the spatial significance level of above noted indices (Fig. 4). The region of High-High mostly extended the significant level of 0.05. The significant level of 0.01 is mainly located in the Low-Low and High-High, expressed that indices have a strong correlation. The region of a significance level of 0.05 is mainly located in the periphery of the main built-up area where the region of significance level extended the 0.01 (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 LISA significance Map in Kanpur Metropolis

Fig. 6. 3D scatterplots of different indices in Kanpur Metropolis

5. Conclusions:

This present study investigates the relation of LST with the selected indices i.e. NDVI, NDBI, NDWI, and NDSI using Landsat8 OLI and TIRS data of Oct. 2020, in Kanpur Metropolis. A correlation, Global Moran's I, and LISA index analyses were done between LST and the selected indices. The correlation of LST with NDBI, NDSI, NDWI, and NDVI have been observed and found that NDBI and NDSI are strongly positively correlated, whereas NDWI is poorly positive correlated. NDVI is weakly negatively related with LST. The values of R^2 are 0.545, 0.525, 0.135, and 0.226 respectively. Correlations of NDBI with NDSI and NDWI have shown a strong positive relationship as shown $R^2 = 0.787$ and 0.407 respectively, further correlation of NDVI with NDBI and NDWI has a strong negative correlation i.e. $R^2 = 0.575$ and 0.962 . The correlation of LST with NDBI is found better than NDSI means more built-up area has high surface temperature. The negative correlation of LST with NDVI indicates that healthy green vegetation lowers the surface temperature. The value of Global Moran's I in LST, NDVI, NDBI, NDWI, and NDSI are 0.400, 0.340, 0.214, 0.377, and 0.238, respectively. The significance level 0.01 of LST and NDVI is mostly reached to the 0.05 in the study area. Further analysis was done by choosing pixels from each Land use and land cover (LULC) of water, vegetation, bare land, and urban built-up areas and plotted to determine the behavior of indices on LST for each LULC. The investigation shows that NDBI and NDSI can be effectively used for the study of LST to draw the urban heat island effect in any urbanized metropolis areas, as well as this study provides a reliable basis for urban construction and planning.

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